

EN3400 – Individual Project

How can IT workloads in data centres be scheduled to align with renewable energy generation and reduce stress on the power grid?

Realistic short-term workload flexibility for low-carbon data centre operation

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Abstract

This dissertation investigates whether realistic short-term flexibility in IT workloads can be used to reduce the environmental impact of data centres. The study focuses on carbon-aware scheduling, in which flexible workloads are shifted to periods with lower grid carbon intensity, higher renewable electricity availability and lower electricity price. Real workload traces are combined with time-varying electricity data, including carbon intensity, renewable generation share and electricity price. Workloads are divided into four flexibility classes with maximum deferral windows of 1, 2 and 3 hours in order to represent realistic operational constraints. Two scheduling strategies are evaluated: a CarbonPriority scheduler, which prioritises minimising carbon emissions, and a Balanced scheduler, which seeks a compromise between emissions reduction and electricity cost reduction. The results show that even limited workload flexibility can reduce both carbon emissions and electricity cost. The CarbonPriority scheduler achieves the greatest emissions reductions, whereas the Balanced scheduler provides a more moderate reduction in emissions while achieving lower operating costs. However, the overall improvements are relatively modest because the majority of the workload is relatively inflexible and can only be delayed for a short period. The report concludes that realistic short-term workload shifting can make a meaningful contribution to reducing the environmental impact of data centres, although it is unlikely to provide very large reductions on its own. Greater benefits will require a combination of workload scheduling, increased renewable electricity supply and further improvements in data centre efficiency.

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1 Introduction

The rapid expansion of cloud computing, artificial intelligence (AI), and digital services has led to a sharp rise in the electricity demand of data centres, which now form a critical part of global infrastructure, supporting communication, entertainment, science, and finance. However, this growth has intensified concerns about the environmental footprint of large-scale computing. Data centres consumed around 415 TWh of electricity worldwide in 2024, roughly 1.5% of global demand, and consumption is expected to increase further as AI workloads grow [1].

Although advances in hardware efficiency and cooling have improved energy performance, these gains have been outweighed by increasing computational demand. Forecasts suggest that global data centre electricity use could nearly double by 2030, adding pressure on energy systems and highlighting the need to reduce carbon intensity and not just overall consumption [1], [2]. This shift towards low-carbon operation has made energy-aware and carbon-aware computing an important research frontier.

One promising strategy is carbon-aware scheduling, which shifts workloads to times when electricity is cleaner or cheaper. Because grid carbon intensity fluctuates throughout the day with changes in renewable generation, delaying flexible tasks to periods of high wind or solar supply can significantly reduce emissions. Previous research indicates that modest workload deferrals can reduce data centre carbon footprints without major performance penalties [3], [4].

This dissertation examines how temporal workload shifting can align data centre demand with renewable energy availability. Using real workload traces and time-varying grid data such as carbon intensity, renewable share, and electricity price, two scheduling strategies are analyzed: CarbonPriority, which minimizes emissions, and Balanced, which optimizes both emissions and cost. By evaluating performance in carbon, cost, renewable alignment, and peak demand metrics, the study aims to assess whether modest temporal flexibility can realistically reduce the environmental impact of data centre operations [5], [6]

The remainder of this dissertation is organized as follows. Chapter 2 reviews the relevant literature on data centre energy consumption, carbon-aware scheduling, workload flexibility and renewable energy integration. Chapter 3 describes the methodology and simulation model used in this study. Chapter 4 presents and discusses the results obtained from the different scheduling strategies. Chapter 5 considers the limitations of the work and provides recommendations for future work, while Chapter 6 summarises the main conclusions. Finally, Chapter 7 discusses the project management aspect of the study.

2 Literature Review

2.1 The Growing Energy Demand of Data Centres

Data centres are now essential to the digital economy, supporting cloud computing, streaming, finance and AI. Their electricity demand has increased rapidly due to rising internet traffic and the expansion of cloud and AI services. Global data centre electricity consumption reached around 415 TWh in 2024, which is approximately 1.5% of worldwide electricity use, and is expected to rise substantially by 2030 [7], [2].

Earlier predictions suggested that data centre energy use would increase in proportion to internet traffic [8]. However, improvements in server efficiency, hardware performance and the growth of hyper-scale facilities slowed this increase between 2010 and 2018 [2], [9]. Recent AI workloads are now driving energy demand upwards again. Training large machine learning models requires much more computation than traditional applications, and can therefore have a substantial carbon footprint [10], [11].

The location and timing of data centre demand are also important. Data centres are often concentrated in areas with low-cost electricity or favourable cooling conditions, which can put pressure on local electricity networks [12].

2.2 Carbon Intensity of Electricity Grids

Electricity grid carbon intensity changes throughout the day because the generation mix varies. When renewable output is high, carbon intensity falls; when fossil-fuel generation is needed, it rises [13], [14]. In the UK, carbon intensity can fall below 100 gCO₂eq/kWh during periods of strong wind generation but rise above 300 gCO₂eq/kWh during winter evenings.

Carbon intensity forecasting is important for carbon-aware scheduling because workloads must often be assigned before future grid conditions are known. Machine learning methods have shown strong performance in predicting future carbon intensity using weather and demand data [15], [16].

Many studies distinguish between average and marginal carbon intensity. Marginal intensity may be more accurate for evaluating the effect of additional electricity demand, but average intensity is more widely available and is therefore more commonly used [17].

2.3 Carbon-Aware Scheduling

Carbon-aware scheduling involves moving computing workloads to times or places where electricity is cleaner [18]. The concept is similar to demand response, where consumers

alter their electricity use in response to grid conditions [19]. Data centres are suited to this because many workloads can be rescheduled in software.

Not all workloads are equally flexible. Interactive services such as web requests and video calls require immediate execution, whereas batch tasks such as backups, analytics and AI training can often be delayed [20], [21]. Temporal shifting delays a workload until a lower-carbon period, while spatial shifting moves it to a different data centre supplied by cleaner electricity [3].

Research has shown that temporal shifting can significantly reduce emissions. Green-Hadoop achieved carbon reductions of up to 39% by aligning workloads with renewable generation [22]. Google has implemented carbon-aware scheduling at large scale, moving around 80% of eligible workloads to lower-carbon hours [23]. Combining temporal and spatial shifting can produce further reductions, although spatial shifting depends on the availability of multiple data centres and sufficient network capacity [24], [3].

2.4 Flexibility Constraints and Workload Classification

The success of carbon-aware scheduling depends on how much workloads can realistically be delayed. In practice, delays are limited by deadlines, service-level agreements and user expectations.

Researchers classify workloads based on the amount of delay they can tolerate, ranging from latency-sensitive interactive services to highly flexible batch workloads [25]. Studies show that even short delays of one to two hours can provide significant carbon savings, especially in grids with high renewable variability [3].

However, excessive deferral can create new problems. If too many workloads are shifted to the same low-carbon period, demand spikes may occur, increasing costs and reducing grid stability. Carbon-aware scheduling therefore requires a balance between reducing emissions and avoiding concentrated peaks in demand [26].

2.5 Scheduling Strategies and Optimisation Methods

A variety of methods have been used for carbon-aware scheduling. Rule-based methods dispatch workloads only when carbon intensity falls below a threshold. These are simple to implement but can perform poorly if low-carbon periods are limited [26].

More advanced approaches use forecasts, reinforcement learning or multi-objective optimization. Reinforcement learning can adapt to changing grid conditions, although it requires large amounts of training data [27]. Multi-objective optimization is useful because it considers carbon emissions, electricity cost and workload delay simultaneously

[28], [29].

Electricity price is sometimes used as a proxy for carbon intensity because prices are often lower when renewable generation is high [30]. However, low prices do not always mean low emissions, so price-based scheduling may overestimate environmental benefits. For this reason, many studies recommend assessing scheduling approaches using several criteria at the same time, including emissions, electricity cost and peak demand, rather than relying on a single metric [28].

2.6 Industry Adoption

Carbon-aware scheduling is increasingly being adopted in industry. Google’s carbon-intelligent computing platform shifts non-urgent workloads to periods with lower forecast carbon intensity [23]. Other cloud providers have also investigated integrating environmental signals into workload management systems, suggesting that carbon-aware scheduling is likely to become more common across industry [31].

Industry adoption is supported by standards such as the Software Carbon Intensity (SCI) specification [32]. In addition, major technology companies are increasingly pursuing the goal of 24/7 carbon-free energy, where electricity demand is matched with clean generation on an hourly basis [6].

Despite this progress, many research systems remain difficult to apply in real data centres because of complex workloads, diverse hardware and operational constraints [33].

2.7 Research Gap

Although previous studies show that carbon-aware scheduling can reduce emissions, several gaps remain. Many studies rely on synthetic workloads or assume unrealistic flexibility windows. Few use real workload traces together with practical delay limits.

In addition, most existing work focuses mainly on carbon emissions, while giving less attention to cost, renewable alignment and peak demand. Results are also often based on a single grid or region, making it difficult to understand how scheduling performance changes under different electricity conditions.

This dissertation addresses these gaps by using real workload traces and realistic delay windows of one, two and three hours. It compares carbon-only and cost-aware scheduling strategies across multiple metrics, including emissions, cost, renewable alignment and peak demand.

3 Methodology

3.1 Workload Dataset and preprocessing

The workload data used in this study was taken from the Alibaba Cluster Trace Program dataset. This dataset records the behaviour of a large production data centre cluster over a period of approximately eight days and includes information about task start times, task durations, CPU demand and memory demand. The dataset has been widely used in previous research because it provides a realistic representation of the behaviour of a modern cloud computing platform and includes both long-running services and transient batch jobs [34], [35].

For the purposes of this report, the machine usage trace was used to construct an hourly CPU utilization profile for the cluster. The original timestamps in the Alibaba dataset are recorded in seconds, so the trace was first converted into hourly intervals. The average CPU utilization of all active machines was then calculated for each hour of the trace.

Because the original data contains short-term fluctuations and irregular spikes, a 24-hour moving average was also calculated. This makes it easier to identify the trend in the workload and confirms whether a daily pattern exists. Previous studies have similarly used smoothing and hourly averaging when analyzing data centre traces in order to remove short-term noise and highlight longer-term patterns in resource demand [9], [36].

Figure 1: Alibaba IT workload: hourly cluster-average CPU utilization and 24-hour moving average.

Figure 1 shows that the workload follows a clear daily cycle. The raw hourly CPU utilization fluctuates between approximately 23% and 57%, with repeated peaks occurring roughly once every 24 hours. The moving average is much smoother and remains between approximately 32% and 42%, confirming that the cluster shows a stable repeating pattern rather than random behaviour.

The largest peaks occur during the middle of the day, while lower utilization is generally observed overnight. This is consistent with the behaviour expected in many real-world data centres, where user activity and batch processing increase during daytime hours. The presence of this repeating daily pattern supports the use of a representative 24-hour average profile in the remainder of the study.

The hourly values were therefore grouped by hour of day and averaged across all eight days of the trace. This produced a single representative 24-hour workload profile, which formed the baseline input to the scheduling model. The incomplete final day in the Alibaba dataset was retained when calculating the moving average but was treated cautiously when interpreting the daily averages, since the trace ends part-way through the final day and therefore contains fewer active tasks.

3.2 Definition of workload scenarios

The Alibaba cluster trace was first processed to obtain a representative 24-hour workload profile. Hourly mean CPU utilisation was calculated from the 8-day trace and then averaged by hour of day to produce a typical daily profile. This profile was treated as the baseline workload scenario because it represents the average behaviour of the cluster over a complete day while removing short-term noise and irregularities.

Figure 2: Alibaba IT workload: baseline, low-burstiness and high-burstiness workload scenarios.

The baseline profile shows a clear daily cycle, with higher utilization during the middle of the day and lower utilization overnight. However, real data centre demand can vary considerably between days. Some days are relatively smooth, whereas others contain sharper peaks and deeper troughs caused by bursts of user activity, large batch jobs or other transient events. To investigate how the effectiveness of the scheduling algorithm changes with the shape of the demand profile, two additional synthetic workload scenarios were created from the baseline profile.

The first additional scenario represented a less bursty workload, while the second represented a more bursty workload. Instead of constructing new demand profiles, the deviations of the baseline profile from its daily mean were scaled. If the original hourly profile is denoted by $W(h)$ and its daily mean by \bar{W} , then the modified profile is given by

$$W_{\text{scenario}}(h) = \bar{W} + \alpha (W(h) - \bar{W}) \quad (1)$$

where α is a scaling factor controlling the magnitude of the deviations from the mean. A value of $\alpha = 0.5$ was used for the low-burstiness case, which reduces the magnitude of peaks and troughs by 50%. A value of $\alpha = 2.0$ was used for the high-burstiness case, which doubles the deviations from the mean and therefore produces larger peaks and deeper troughs. The resulting values were then limited to the physically realistic range of 0–100% CPU utilization.

This approach keeps the overall daily shape of the original workload while allowing the effect of different levels of burstiness to be examined in a controlled manner. Similar methods have previously been used in studies of data centre and electricity demand modelling, where the shape of a baseline load profile is retained but its amplitude is scaled in order to test system sensitivity under different operating conditions [36], [9].

3.3 Workload flexibility classification

The scheduling model requires an estimate of how much of the workload can realistically be delayed. The Alibaba trace does not contain an explicit measure of workload flexibility. Therefore, a proxy flexibility score was derived from the characteristics of each batch task using a separate Alibaba dataset. This approach is consistent with previous studies, which infer the flexibility of jobs from their resource requirements, duration and repeatability rather than relying on an explicitly labelled flexibility field [35], [34].

Three task characteristics were used:

- average CPU demand
- runtime

- repeatability of the task or job identifier

Tasks with lower CPU demand were assumed to be more flexible because smaller jobs are generally easier to move without affecting overall cluster performance. Longer-running jobs were also assumed to be more flexible, since they are more likely to contain some slack or non-urgent processing time. Finally, tasks that appeared repeatedly within the trace were assumed to be more suitable for shifting because repetitive jobs are often associated with scheduled background processes or recurring batch workloads [34], [3].

Each characteristic was first normalized to the range 0-1 using

$$\hat{x} = \frac{x - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}} \quad (2)$$

where x is the original value of the variable being normalized, x_{\min} is the minimum value of that variable within the dataset, and x_{\max} is the corresponding maximum value. This normalization scales the variable to a dimensionless range between 0 and 1, allowing different quantities to be compared and combined consistently.

The CPU term was then inverted so that lower CPU demand corresponded to greater flexibility. The final composite flexibility score was defined as

$$F = w_{\text{cpu}}(1 - \hat{C}) + w_{\text{runtime}}\hat{R} + w_{\text{repeat}}\hat{P} \quad (3)$$

where \hat{C} is the normalized CPU demand, \hat{R} is the normalized runtime and \hat{P} is the normalized repeatability score. The weighting factors were chosen as

$$w_{\text{cpu}} = 0.4, \quad w_{\text{runtime}} = 0.4, \quad w_{\text{repeat}} = 0.2$$

giving

$$F = 0.4(1 - \hat{C}) + 0.4\hat{R} + 0.2\hat{P} \quad (4)$$

The larger weighting given to CPU demand and runtime reflects the assumption that these are the most important indicators of whether a task can be delayed, while repeatability is treated as a secondary factor because it is less directly related to temporal flexibility. Similar weighted scoring approaches have been used in previous work on job scheduling and workload prioritisation in cloud and cluster systems [35], [41].

Once the flexibility score had been calculated for each task, tasks were grouped according to the percentiles of the score distribution:

- bottom 25%: inflexible / low flexibility

- 25–50%: conservative flexibility
- 50–75%: moderate flexibility
- top 25%: high flexibility

Each flexibility class was then mapped to a maximum deferral window:

- inflexible / low flexibility: ≤ 30 min
- conservative flexibility: ≤ 1 h
- moderate flexibility: ≤ 2 h
- high flexibility: ≤ 3 h

These deferral windows were selected to represent realistic levels of flexibility [44]. Previous research has shown that many data centre tasks can only be delayed for a short period before deadlines or service quality are affected, and that assuming long delay windows can overestimate the achievable benefits of scheduling [31], [37]. Consequently, the present study deliberately limits the maximum delay to 3 hours.

Figure 3: Average 24-hour workload composition by maximum deferral window.

Figure 3 demonstrates that the proportion of highly flexible workload is greatest during the late morning and early afternoon, while the evening period contains a larger proportion of less flexible demand. This temporal variation is important because it determines whether flexible jobs are available during periods of low-carbon or low-cost electricity. The hourly flexibility profile therefore formed a direct input to the scheduling model.

3.4 Electricity system input data

In addition to the workload trace, the scheduling model requires information about the state of the electricity system. Three external signals were used:

- grid carbon intensity
- renewable electricity percentage
- day-ahead electricity price

These signals were obtained from the Electricity Maps platform for four representative dates in 2025:

- 15 March
- 21 June
- 15 September
- 21 December

The four dates were selected to represent spring, summer, autumn and winter conditions. Using four dates rather than a single day makes it possible to examine how the effectiveness of the scheduling algorithm changes throughout the year.

In addition, the scheduling model was tested using electricity system data from Great Britain, Spain, Ontario and New Zealand in order to capture a range of climates and electricity generation mixes. These regions were selected because they represent different seasonal patterns, renewable resources and carbon intensity profiles. Only a subset of the results is presented in this dissertation due to space limitations. Ontario was chosen instead of all of Canada because province-level data produced clearer and more distinct scheduling behaviour than the national average.

Previous research has shown that the carbon intensity of electricity systems varies substantially throughout the day and between seasons because the electricity generation mix changes over time [31], [37]. Similarly, renewable output and electricity price are strongly influenced by weather conditions, daylight hours and demand patterns [39]. It is therefore important that the scheduling algorithm is tested under a range of different electricity system conditions rather than only a single scenario.

3.4.1 Carbon intensity

The first signal was the carbon intensity of the Great Britain electricity grid, measured in grams of carbon dioxide per kilowatt-hour (gCO_2/kWh). Carbon intensity is lower when the grid contains a larger proportion of renewable or nuclear generation and higher when electricity is generated primarily from fossil fuels such as gas or coal.

Figure 4: Great Britain hourly average carbon intensity for 15 March, 21 June, 15 September and 21 December 2025.

Figure 4 shows that carbon intensity varies significantly throughout both the day and the year. The highest values generally occur during the evening period, particularly between approximately 17:00 and 21:00 (All times are in UTC). This is most noticeable on 15 March and 21 June, where the evening carbon intensity rises sharply to around 185 gCO_2/kWh and 130 gCO_2/kWh respectively.

In contrast, the lowest carbon intensities tend to occur during the late morning and early afternoon. For example, on 15 September the carbon intensity falls to approximately 35 gCO_2/kWh during the middle of the day. This pattern suggests that there may be opportunities to reduce emissions by shifting flexible computing demand away from the evening peak and towards lower-carbon periods.

3.4.2 Renewable electricity percentage

The second external signal was the proportion of total electricity demand supplied by renewable generation. This includes technologies such as wind, solar and hydro power. The renewable percentage provides an alternative measure of how favourable each hour is for scheduling. Hours with a higher renewable percentage are desirable because they

indicate that a greater proportion of electricity is being produced from low-carbon sources.

Figure 5: Great Britain hourly average renewable electricity percentage for 15 March, 21 June, 15 September and 21 December 2025

Figure 5 shows that the renewable percentage is generally highest during the middle of the day and lower during the evening. On 15 September, the renewable share reaches more than 80% between approximately 09:00 and 15:00. In contrast, the March profile only reaches around 55%, while the December profile remains below 65% throughout the day.

The seasonal differences are mainly caused by changes in solar generation and electricity demand. September and June benefit from longer daylight hours and stronger renewable output, whereas winter conditions result in lower renewable penetration. The figure therefore supports the expectation that the scheduling algorithm may achieve greater improvements during some seasons than others.

3.4.3 Day-ahead electricity price

The third external signal was the day-ahead electricity price, measured in GBP/MWh. Day-ahead prices were included because data centre operators are concerned not only with reducing carbon emissions but also with reducing operating cost. Electricity prices are typically highest when demand is high or when expensive fossil-fuel generation is required to meet that demand [40].

Figure 6: Great Britain hourly average day-ahead electricity price for 15 March, 21 June, 15 September and 21 December 2025

Figure 6 shows that the price profile differs considerably between seasons. The highest prices generally occur during the evening period, especially between approximately 17:00 and 20:00. For example, on 15 March the price rises to around 125 GBP/MWh during the evening peak, while on 21 June it exceeds 110 GBP/MWh.

By contrast, prices are much lower during the late morning and early afternoon. On 21 June, prices fall to around 20 GBP/MWh between approximately 12:00 and 14:00. Similarly, on 15 September the price is close to zero during the middle of the day.

The broad similarity between the carbon intensity and electricity price profiles suggests that the cleanest periods are often also the cheapest. However, this relationship is not perfect, particularly during winter conditions. Consequently, the scheduling model considered both carbon intensity and electricity price rather than assuming that minimising one would always minimise the other.

3.5 Scheduling algorithm

The purpose of the scheduling algorithm was to investigate whether a portion of the workload could be shifted from less favourable hours to more favourable hours. In this context, a favourable hour is one with lower carbon intensity, higher renewable percentage and lower electricity price.

The scheduling process was carried out in three stages:

1. the workload was divided into flexibility classes

2. a score was assigned to every hour of the day
3. flexible workload was moved to the highest-scoring hours, subject to the deferral limits defined previously

The algorithm operated on an hourly basis. The inflexible workload remained fixed, while the flexible portion of the workload could be moved by up to 1, 2 or 3 hours depending on its flexibility class.

A combined scheduling score was calculated for each hour using the normalised values of the external electricity system signals. The score was defined as

$$S = w_R \hat{R} + w_C(1 - \hat{C}) + w_P(1 - \hat{P}) + w_G(1 - \hat{G}) \quad (5)$$

where:

- \hat{R} is the normalised renewable percentage
- \hat{C} is the normalised carbon intensity
- \hat{P} is the normalised electricity price
- \hat{G} is the normalised gas share of the electricity mix

The carbon, price and gas terms were inverted so that lower values corresponded to more desirable hours. The weighting factors used in the model were

$$w_R = 0.35, \quad w_C = 0.30, \quad w_P = 0.20, \quad w_G = 0.15$$

giving

$$S = 0.35\hat{R} + 0.3(1 - \hat{C}) + 0.2(1 - \hat{P}) + 0.15(1 - \hat{G}) \quad (6)$$

These values were chosen so that the scheduling decision was influenced primarily by renewable availability and carbon intensity, while still taking cost into account. Similar weighted multi-objective scheduling methods have previously been used in carbon-aware and renewable-aware data centre scheduling studies [31], [41].

Two scheduling strategies were examined:

- CarbonPriority ($w_R = 0.40, w_C = 0.40, w_P = 0.10, w_G = 0.10$)
- Balanced (values in eq. (6))

The CarbonPriority strategy placed greater emphasis on minimising carbon emissions, whereas the Balanced strategy attempted to reduce both carbon emissions and electricity cost by using the values mentioned in (6). The same workload scenarios and flexibility limits were used in both cases.

For each hour, the scheduler searched for the best alternative hour within the permitted deferral window. Flexible workload was moved only if the destination hour had a higher scheduling score than the original hour. A small delay penalty was also included so that the algorithm preferred shorter shifts where possible. This prevented the model from always moving tasks to the single best hour of the day and is consistent with previous studies that include delay penalties or deadline constraints in order to produce more realistic scheduling behaviour [37], [3].

A capacity limit was also applied. The scheduled workload in any hour was not allowed to exceed the maximum value of the original baseline profile. This constraint prevents the creation of unrealistically large peaks and reflects the practical reality that data centres have finite processing capacity.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 CarbonPriority scheduling results

Figure 7: CarbonPriority scheduler results showing carbon reduction, cost reduction, renewable alignment and peak reduction for all country-date and workload scenarios.

Figure 7 shows that the CarbonPriority strategy consistently produces a reduction in carbon emissions for almost every scenario. The largest reductions occur for the high-burstiness workload, particularly in Great Britain and Ontario.

For Great Britain on 15 March, the baseline workload produces a carbon reduction of approximately 0.7%, while the high-burstiness workload increases this to around 0.9%. A similar trend is observed on 21 June, where the reduction rises from approximately 1.3% for the baseline case to around 1.7%. The greatest reduction in the figure occurs for Ontario on 15 March, where the high-burstiness workload achieves a reduction of approximately 2%, compared with around 1.6% for the baseline workload.

The low-burstiness workload generally provides the smallest improvement. In several cases, such as Spain on 21 June and Spain on 15 September, the low-burstiness workload produces almost no carbon reduction and in some cases appears slightly negative.

The cost reduction heatmap in Figure 7 shows that CarbonPriority also produces modest cost savings, even though cost is not its primary objective. The largest reductions again occur for the high-burstiness workload. In Great Britain on 15 September, the cost reduction reaches approximately 6% for the high-burstiness case, compared with around 5% for the baseline workload. Spain on 15 March shows a smaller but still noticeable trend, with cost savings increasing from approximately 2.5% for the baseline workload to around 3.5% for the high-burstiness case.

However, the cost reductions are generally smaller in Ontario and New Zealand. In these regions, most scenarios show cost savings of less than 1%, and in several New Zealand cases the reduction is close to zero.

The renewable alignment results show that CarbonPriority consistently shifts more workload into periods with higher renewable generation. The largest increase occurs for Spain on 15 September, where the high-burstiness workload produces an increase in renewable alignment of approximately 4%. Great Britain on 21 December and 15 March also show noticeable improvements of around 1-2%.

By contrast, the increase in renewable alignment is generally below 1% for New Zealand and Ontario.

The final heatmap in Figure 7 shows the change in peak workload. In most cases, the peak is reduced slightly rather than increased. Great Britain shows the largest reduction, with all workload on 15 September producing a peak reduction of approximately 3%. Spain also shows a reduction of approximately 3% across most workload scenarios.

Importantly, none of the scenarios create a substantial increase in peak demand. This confirms that the capacity limit built into the scheduling algorithm successfully prevents the creation of unrealistic new peaks.

4.2 Balanced scheduling results

Figure 8: Balanced scheduler results showing carbon reduction, cost reduction, renewable alignment and peak reduction for all country-date and workload scenarios.

Figure 8 shows the results of the Balanced strategy. Compared with CarbonPriority, the Balanced method generally produces slightly smaller reductions in carbon emissions but somewhat larger reductions in electricity cost.

For Great Britain on 15 March, the baseline workload achieves a carbon reduction of approximately 0.6% under the Balanced strategy, compared with around 0.7% under CarbonPriority. Similarly, the high-burstiness workload achieves a reduction of approximately 0.8%, which is slightly lower than the roughly 0.9% achieved by CarbonPriority.

The same pattern is visible across most other scenarios. Ontario on 15 March again shows very high reduction, but the value falls slightly from approximately 2.0% under CarbonPriority to around 1.3% under Balanced for the high-burstiness workload.

The main advantage of the Balanced strategy can be seen in the cost reduction heatmap. For Great Britain on 15 September, the baseline workload achieves a cost reduction of approximately 6.5%, while the high-burstiness workload reaches around 7.0–7.5%. These values are slightly larger than those achieved by CarbonPriority.

Interestingly, for Spain on 15 March, the high-burstiness workload produces a cost reduction of approximately 3.5%, compared with around 4.0% under CarbonPriority. In Ontario on 15 March, the baseline workload produces a cost reduction of approximately 5.5% under the Balanced strategy, compared with around 2.5% under CarbonPriority.

The renewable alignment heatmap in Figure 8 shows a similar pattern to CarbonPriority, although the improvements are generally slightly smaller. Spain on 15 September produces the largest increase, with the high-burstiness workload increasing renewable alignment by approximately 4%. Great Britain and Spain continue to show larger improvements than Ontario and New Zealand, where the changes are usually below 1%.

The peak reduction heatmap shows that Balanced has almost the same effect on peak demand as CarbonPriority. Great Britain and Spain again experience the largest reductions, typically between 2% and 3%, while Ontario and New Zealand show only small changes.

Therefore, the main difference between the two strategies lies in the trade-off between carbon reduction and cost reduction. CarbonPriority achieves the greatest reduction in emissions, whereas Balanced achieves the greatest reduction in cost.

4.3 Example of hourly workload shifting

Figure 9: Baseline workload before and after scheduling, shown alongside carbon intensity, renewable percentage and electricity price for Great Britain.

These graphs are for the Balanced scheduler.

The upper-left graph shows that the workload is shifted away from the evening period and redistributed towards the middle of the day. The original workload reaches a peak of approximately 55% CPU utilisation at around 06:00, while a second high-demand period occurs between 17:00 and 20:00. After scheduling, the evening workload is reduced by around 3–4%, while the midday workload increases from approximately 35% to around 40%.

The upper-right graph shows that carbon intensity is highest during the evening, reaching approximately 185 gCO₂/kWh between 18:00 and 20:00. By contrast, the lowest values, approximately 105 gCO₂/kWh, occur between 10:00 and 14:00. The scheduled workload therefore increases mainly during this lower-carbon midday period and decreases during the higher-carbon evening period.

The lower-left graph shows that renewable penetration reaches its maximum value of approximately 57% between 11:00 and 13:00, compared with only around 30–35% during the evening. The scheduled workload is highest during the same midday period, indicating that a larger proportion of demand is supplied when renewable generation is greatest.

The lower-right graph shows that electricity price follows a similar pattern. Prices reach approximately 125 GBP/MWh at around 18:00, but fall to around 85–95 GBP/MWh during the middle of the day. Consequently, the scheduled workload is reduced during the most expensive hours and increased during the cheapest hours.

Overall, the figure shows that the largest scheduling changes occur when the difference between midday and evening conditions is greatest.

4.4 Discussion

The results show that realistic short-term workload flexibility can reduce both carbon emissions and electricity cost, although the reductions are relatively modest. In almost all cases, the high-burstiness workload produces the greatest benefit. For example, under the CarbonPriority strategy, the high-burstiness workload in Ontario on 15 March reduces carbon emissions by approximately 2%, compared with around 1.6% for the baseline workload. Under the Balanced strategy, the same scenario still produces a relatively large reduction, although the value falls to around 1.3%.

This indicates that the shape of the workload profile strongly affects scheduling performance. A burstier workload contains larger peaks that can be shifted away from high-carbon and high-cost hours, whereas a smoother workload is already spread more evenly across the day and therefore offers less opportunity for improvement. This can be seen particularly in the low-burstiness cases for Spain on 21 June and 15 September, where the carbon reduction is close to zero or slightly negative.

The achievable reductions also depend strongly on the electricity system. Great Britain and Spain consistently produce the largest improvements in cost and renewable alignment because their electricity systems vary more strongly throughout the day. Great Britain achieves cost reductions of around 5–6% under CarbonPriority and up to 8% under Balanced for September 15, while Spain achieves renewable alignment improvements of up to 4% on 15 September. These larger improvements occur because both regions experience strong daily changes in carbon intensity, renewable generation and electricity

price.

By contrast, Ontario and New Zealand generally achieve smaller cost reductions and renewable alignment improvements. In New Zealand, most cost reductions remain below 1%, while renewable alignment in both Ontario and New Zealand is usually below 1%. However, Ontario still achieves some of the largest carbon reductions because its carbon intensity varies sufficiently throughout the day despite relatively stable electricity prices. This is shown by the Ontario 15 March case, where the high-burstiness workload achieves a 2% carbon emissions reduction under CarbonPriority.

The comparison between CarbonPriority and Balanced highlights a clear trade-off between reducing emissions and reducing cost. CarbonPriority consistently achieves the largest emissions reduction. For example, in Great Britain on 15 March, the high-burstiness workload reduces emissions by approximately 0.9% under CarbonPriority compared with around 0.8% under Balanced. However, Balanced usually produces larger cost savings because electricity price forms part of the scheduling score. In Great Britain on 15 September, the high-burstiness workload reduces cost by approximately 8% under Balanced, compared with approximately 6% under CarbonPriority.

Although these reductions are smaller than those reported in some previous studies, they are likely to be more realistic. Earlier work often assumed that large fractions of the workload could be delayed by many hours, leading to reported carbon reductions of 10–20% or more [42], [43]. In this dissertation, however, the maximum delay was limited to 3 hours and most of the workload remained inflexible, so the reductions generally stayed below around 2–3%. This agrees with Sukprasert et al. [39], who found that realistic operational constraints significantly reduce the potential of carbon-aware scheduling. The findings are also consistent with Radovanovic et al. [37], who showed that even small changes in workload timing can still produce worthwhile emissions savings at a large scale. A daily carbon reduction of around 1–2% and a few percent saving in electricity cost could add up to a substantial improvement over the course of a year, particularly for large data centres operating continuously.

5 Limitations and Future Work

Although the results show that carbon-aware scheduling can reduce both carbon emissions and electricity cost, several limitations should be recognised. The workload model was based mainly on the Alibaba Cluster Trace dataset, which represents only one cloud environment over approximately eight days. Other facilities, such as AI training clusters or high-performance computing systems, may have different demand patterns and greater flexibility. In particular, AI workloads are often more bursty and may contain a larger proportion of delay-tolerant tasks. Therefore, the results may not be directly applicable

to all data centres.

A further limitation is that workload flexibility was not known directly and had to be estimated from task duration, CPU demand and repeatability. Similar proxy approaches have been used in previous studies [35], [34], but they cannot determine with certainty whether a task could be delayed without affecting deadlines or service-level agreements. The assumed delay windows of 1, 2 and 3 hours should therefore be regarded as approximate.

The scheduling model was also simplified. Only temporal shifting within a single data centre was considered, whereas previous work has shown that larger carbon reductions may be possible through geographical load balancing between multiple sites [3]. In addition, the model assumed perfect knowledge of future carbon intensity, renewable generation and electricity price, whereas in practice these values would need to be forecast and forecast errors could reduce performance.

Finally, the electricity system analysis was based on only four representative days in 2025 and on regional average data. These days do not capture the full variation in weather, renewable generation and electricity demand throughout the year. Future work could therefore use longer workload traces, include AI and high-performance computing workloads, and investigate more advanced scheduling methods such as mixed-integer optimisation or reinforcement learning [31]. It would also be valuable to examine the interaction between workload shifting and other decarbonisation measures, such as on-site renewables, battery storage and improved cooling efficiency.

6 Conclusion

This dissertation investigated whether IT workloads in data centres can be scheduled to better align with renewable electricity generation and thus reduce both carbon emissions and electricity cost. A scheduling model was developed using workload traces from the Alibaba Cluster Trace dataset together with time-varying electricity data, including carbon intensity, renewable generation percentage and day-ahead electricity price. Unlike many previous studies, the model assumed realistic workload flexibility, with most tasks either fixed or limited to delays of between one and three hours.

The results showed that even modest flexibility can provide worthwhile benefits. Both scheduling strategies shifted part of the workload away from the evening period, when electricity was generally more carbon-intensive and expensive, towards the middle of the day, when renewable generation was higher and carbon intensity lower. The CarbonPriority strategy consistently produced the largest reduction in carbon emissions, while the Balanced strategy generally achieved the greatest reduction in electricity cost.

The greatest improvements were seen in Great Britain and Spain, where there were large

differences between low-carbon and high-carbon periods of the day. Smaller improvements occurred in Ontario and New Zealand because these electricity systems already contain a high proportion of low-carbon generation. The shape of the workload profile was also important. The high-burstiness workload achieved the largest reductions because its sharper peaks could be shifted more effectively, whereas the low-burstiness workload offered less opportunity for improvement.

Although the reductions in emissions and cost were generally only a few percent, they remain significant given the large electricity demand of modern data centres. Even a small percentage reduction could correspond to substantial annual savings in both emissions and operating cost. However, the findings also show that workload scheduling alone is unlikely to provide a complete solution, since much of the workload remains inflexible. The greatest long-term benefit is therefore likely to come from combining carbon-aware scheduling with other measures, such as more efficient hardware, improved cooling and increased use of renewable electricity.

7 Project Management Reflection

A Gantt chart and risk register were used throughout the project to manage progress and identify potential issues. The work was planned in five stages: understanding the topic, completing the literature review, collecting data, producing results and writing the dissertation. Although this structure remained unchanged, data collection and modelling took longer than expected, so some parts of the literature review and analysis had to be completed simultaneously.

The main change during the project was to broaden the focus from AI workloads specifically to IT workloads in general, because suitable public datasets for AI workloads were limited. The use of the Alibaba Cluster Trace dataset allowed the study to be based on realistic workload data while still considering AI workloads where relevant.

The main risks identified were time management, limited data availability and technical issues with MATLAB modelling. These risks were managed through weekly targets, regular progress reviews, use of multiple data sources and frequent testing of the code. Overall, the project management tools helped keep the project organised and achievable despite the changes made during the work.

The black section in the following gantt chart represents the exam period in which it wasn't reasonable to do extensive work on the project due to the focus on the preparation for the exams.

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Weekly Meeting Records

Date	Attendees	Summary of discussion and actions
10 Oct 2025	Student, Supervisor	Discussed the overall project area and refined the title to focus specifically on how IT workloads in data centres can be scheduled to align with renewable energy generation and reduce stress on the power grid. Agreed that the project should examine both environmental and economic impacts rather than only total energy use. Initial tasks were set, including carrying out background reading on data centre energy demand, grid carbon intensity, renewable generation patterns and carbon-aware scheduling.
24 Oct 2025	Student, Supervisor	Reviewed findings from the initial literature review. Discussed the differences between carbon-aware, cost-aware and renewable-aware scheduling and identified the main research gap: many studies use unrealistic flexibility assumptions and do not consider cost, renewable alignment and peak demand together. Agreed that the dissertation should compare a carbon-only scheduling strategy with a more balanced approach that also considers electricity price.

Date	Attendees	Summary of discussion and actions
07 Nov 2025	Student, Supervisor	Discussed possible workload datasets for the project. Considered the Google Borg and Alibaba cluster traces and agreed that the Alibaba dataset would be most suitable because it contains realistic CPU demand, task duration and runtime information. Also discussed the need to classify workloads according to how much they can realistically be delayed.
21 Nov 2025	Student, Supervisor	Reviewed progress on obtaining and cleaning the Alibaba workload trace. Discussed problems with timestamp formats and how to convert the original data into hourly CPU utilisation profiles. Agreed that the workload should be separated into fixed and flexible components and that smoothing methods such as a moving average could be used to make the trends clearer.
05 Dec 2025	Student, Supervisor	Discussed which external electricity system data should be used. Agreed that carbon intensity, renewable electricity percentage and day-ahead electricity price should all be included because they represent the main factors affecting sustainable workload scheduling. Considered several regions with different climates and electricity systems, including Great Britain, Spain, Ontario and New Zealand.
30 Jan 2026	Student, Supervisor	Reviewed the first version of the scheduling algorithm. Discussed how the scheduler should search for the best hour within the allowed delay window and only shift work if there is a clear improvement in carbon intensity or scheduling score. Agreed to include a delay penalty so that the algorithm would prefer shorter shifts where possible.

Date	Attendees	Summary of discussion and actions
13 Feb 2026	Student, Supervisor	Discussed how the two scheduling strategies should be defined. Agreed that the first strategy, CarbonPriority, should optimise only for low carbon intensity, while the second strategy, Balanced, should include both carbon intensity and electricity price. Also discussed the weighting values used in the balanced score and how they could affect the final results.
27 Feb 2026	Student, Supervisor	Discussed how the results should be presented in the dissertation. Agreed that the main comparison should focus on changes in carbon emissions, electricity cost, renewable alignment and peak demand. Also decided that only the clearest and most representative graphs should be included in the main report.
